

Earnings Management, Supervisory Board Effectiveness, and Company Value

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ABSTRACT: Income smoothing is a form of earnings management that manipulates the profits reported in the annual financial report, motivated by managers' bonuses. This investigation examines the effects of supervisory board effectiveness — reflected in its size and independence — on income smoothing in non-financial companies in the LQ45 index in Indonesia from 2017 to 2023, followed by the relationship between income smoothing and company value. Income smoothing and company value are measured by the inverse of the Eckel Index and by the natural logarithm of the stock price, respectively. Meanwhile, the size and independence are quantified separately as the number of commissioners and the proportion of independent commissioners among the total commissioners. The samples used consist of nine companies. Moreover, the path analysis model is used to test the hypotheses, with t-statistics provided to support them. This investigation finds that the fewer people on the commissioner board, the lower income smoothing. The proportion of independent commissioners negatively affects income smoothing practices, suggesting that greater board independence improves oversight and limits earnings management. Because of successful supervision, income smoothing disappeared in the market, as evidenced by the meaningless association between income smoothing and company value. In practice, this study suggests that companies adopt a smaller supervisory board and greater independence to reduce income smoothing. Thus, the adverse effect of income smoothing disappears in the market.

KEYWORDS: Include at least 5 to 6 keywords or phrases

I. INTRODUCTION

For companies listed on the capital market, managers no longer focus solely on achieving profit but also on the value of the company they manage — namely, the share price — which reflects shareholder welfare (Hanafi, 2016). However, several previous researchers believe that share prices are influenced by their capability to generate profits (Akhmadi & Januarsi, 2021; Dang, Hoang, et al., 2018; Dang, Tran, et al., 2018).

Because of their efforts to achieve profits, managers receive a bonus from the owners (Amananto & Suwarti, 2023). However, to get it, managers manage earnings reporting. They smooth profits by reporting profits; therefore, profits do not exceed the upper or lower limits for bonus eligibility. For excess profit not reported in the current period, managers report it in the subsequent period, thereby receiving the bonuses promised by the company owners periodically (Sulistyanto, 2018).

Ideally, income-smoothing practices reduce company value, as several researchers, including Abogun et al. (2021) and Aguguom and Salawu (2022), based on data from companies listed on the Nigerian capital market, and Dyussemina et al. (2024), based on Korean data, have stated. A different finding was confirmed by Ozundu et al. (2025), who reported that income smoothing did not affect company value, as measured by the Tobin Q, in the South African and Nigerian capital markets. Similarly, Kirana (2020) confirms this meaningless tendency after investigating the manufacturing companies in the Indonesian capital market.

The effectiveness of the supervisory board is evident from its size and independence, particularly in mitigating managerial tendency to engage in income smoothing. The question is whether a large or a small supervisory board can reduce income smoothing. Additionally, does the supervisory board affect income smoothing?

- If a large supervisory board effectively reduces income smoothing, a negative relationship occurs, as shown by Kustono (2021).
- If a small supervisory board effectively reduces income smoothing, a positive relationship is observed, as demonstrated by Ratnaningsih and Mashelia (2020).
- Meanwhile, other related research shows that the size of the supervisory board does not affect income smoothing, as demonstrated by Dickson (2021).

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Regarding the independence of the supervisory board, ideally, the higher the level of board independence, the lower the tendency of managers to smooth income, as shown by Ekadjaja et al. (2020), Dickson (2021), and Maryanti et al. (2023). However, these results are still inconsistent. In his research, Kustono (2021) and Holinata and Yanti (2021) documented the absence of such a relationship.

Given ongoing research findings, this study aims to reexamine the influence of the supervisory board and its level of independence on income smoothing for non-financial companies selected for the LQ45 Index from 2017 to 2023, as LQ45 companies span multiple sectors. Additionally, this study examines the effect of income smoothing on company value. This research model distinguishes itself from previous studies, which have only investigated the influence of the size of the supervisory board and its level of independence on company value (Dickson, 2021; Kustono, 2021; Ratnaningsih & Mashelia, 2020).

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

Income smoothing is a part of earnings management. With income smoothing, public shareholders do not receive accurate information about the profitable company. Therefore, asymmetric information, shown by signaling theory, exists (Ozundu et al., 2025). If the market is aware of this situation, the firm's value will decrease, as Abogun et al. (2021), Agugom and Salawu (2022), and Dyussemina et al. (2024) demonstrate.

Resource dependency theory suggests that a large number of supervisory boards are required (Pfeffer, 1972), a finding confirmed by Kustono (2021), who confirmed a negative relationship between their size and income smoothing.

Agency theory suggests a small number of supervisory boards (Lipton & Lorsch, 1992), as confirmed by Ratnaningsih and Mashelia (2020), who affirmed a positive relationship between their size and income smoothing. According to a similar theory, the supervisory board's independence can decrease income smoothing. In their research, Ekadjaja et al. (2020), Dickson (2021), and Maryanti et al. (2023) confirm this theory by showing a negative association between board independence and income smoothing.

III. METHODS

There are two exogenous variables: the size of the supervisory board and its independence. Meanwhile, income smoothing and firm value are endogenous variables. The measurement of these variables is presented in Table 1.

Table 1. The measurement of variables

Variable position	name of the variable	Indicator	Source
Exogeneous	Supervisory board size	The number of the supervisory board	Kustono (2021)
	Supervisory board independence	The outside to total supervisory board ratio	Kustono (2021) and Ekadjaja et al. (2020)
Endogeneous	Income smoothing	The Eckel index = the coefficient of variation (CV) of the change in income divided by the CV of the change in revenue.	Yang et al. (2012), Holinata and Yanti (2021), and Setiana et al. (2025),
	Firm value	The natural logarithm of the stock price	Modified from Agugom and Salawu (2022) and Kirana (2020)

Notes: Income smoothing occurs when the Eckel index is less than 1 (Yang et al., 2012); therefore, in the analyses, this study uses 1/the Eckel index to support the related directional hypotheses (Setiana et al., 2025).

Regarding the research sample, the researchers selected 15 non-financial issuers from the LQ45 index, covering the period from 2017 to 2023. The issuers are:

- (1) Adaro Energy Tbk (ADRO)
- (2) Aneka Tambang (Persero) Tbk. (ANTM)
- (3) Astra International Tbk. (ASII)
- (4) XL Axiata Tbk. (EXCL)
- (5) Indofood CBP Sukses Makmur Tbk. (ICBP)
- (6) International Nickel Indonesia Tbk (INCO)
- (7) Indofood Sukses Makmur Tbk. (INDF)
- (8) Indocement Tunggak Prakasa Tbk (INTP)
- (9) Kalbe Farma Tbk (KLBF)
- (10) Perusahaan Gas Negara (Persero) Tbk. (PGAS)
- (11) Tambang Batubara Bukit Asam Tbk. (PTBA)

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- (12) Semen Indonesia (Persero) Tbk. (SMGR)
- (13) Telekomunikasi Indonesia Tbk (TLKM)
- (14) United Tractors Tbk. (UNTR)
- (15) Unilever Indonesia Tbk. (UNVR)

Using a 10% margin of error, this study yields 13 companies using the Slovin formula. Then, simple random sampling is used to select them. Unfortunately, this study only utilizes nine firms coded (1) ADRO, (2) ANTM, (3) INDF, (4) KLBF, (5) PGAS, (6) PTBA, (7) SMGR, (8) TLKM, and (9) UNTR. This situation occurs because this study aims to create the ideal conditions for hypothesis testing, as Erna et al. (2024) and Setiana et al. (2025) state. Furthermore, this study employs archival techniques to collect secondary data, as explained by Hartono (2014), and a path analysis model, as described by Ghozali (2021), presented in the Figure below.

Figure 1. Research Model

In IBM SPSS, path analysis involves a regression model with equations (Ghozali, 2021). In this research context, two equations are as follows: (1) $IS = f(SBN \text{ and } SBI)$ and (2) $FV = f(IS)$. Thus, the normality, heteroskedasticity, and autocorrelation testing become essential for Equations 1 and 2, and multicollinearity is vital for Equation 1 (Ghozali, 2021). To test for normality, heteroskedasticity, and autocorrelation, this study uses the Jarque-Bera test (Sugiyanto et al., 2022), the White test (Sugiyanto et al., 2022), and the runs test (Ghozali, 2021), respectively.

IV. RESULTS

This study uses only nine non-financial companies from the LQ45 index for the period 2017 to 2023. Hence, 63 observations exist, and the statistical descriptions of each variable, including minimum, maximum, mean, and standard deviation, are presented in Table 2. Moreover, the minimum, maximum, mean, and standard deviation for:

- a. The supervisory board size is 5, 12, 7.0317, and 1.58591, respectively.
- b. The supervisory board independence is 0.25, 0.67, 0.3808, and 0.07943, one-to-one.
- c. After the inverse of Excel index, the income smoothing values are -4.89, 7.08, 1.0970, and 1.37380, respectively.
- d. The stock prices before the natural logarithm transformation are IDR 625, IDR 35,400, IDR 6,247.10, and IDR 7,701.318, respectively.

Table 2. The result of descriptive statistics

Variable	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Standard deviation
Supervisory board size	5.00	12.00	7.0317	1.58591
Supervisory board independence	0.25	0.67	0.3808	0.07943
Income smoothing (after the inverse of Excel index)	-4.89	7.08	1.0970	1.37380
Stock price (before natural logarithm transformation)	625	35400	6247.10	7701.318

Table 3 depicts the related introduction tests of the two models. For normality testing, the Jarque-Bera statistic for Model 1 is 0.000, which is less than the 5% significance level (α), indicating that the residuals do not follow a normal distribution. This situation is acceptable because the 63 observations exceed 30, as the central limit theorem predicts (Islam, 2018). For Model 2, the normality of the errors exists because the p-value is higher than $\alpha = 5\%$: 0.113. Besides, there is no heteroskedasticity problem in Models 1 and 2 because the p-values for the R-squared are greater than $\alpha = 5\%$: 0.391 and 0.914. Similarly, there is no autocorrelation because the asymptotic significance is 0.856 for Models 1 and 2. Equally, Model 1 is free of multicollinearity because the VIF is less than 10: 1.009.

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Table 3. The result of the normality, heteroskedasticity, autocorrelation, and multicollinearity examination

Examination Required	The Technique	Measurement	The results	
			Model 1: IS = f(SBN, SBI)	Model 2: FV = f (IS)
Normality	Jarque-Bera Statistic	The probability of the J-B statistic	0.000	0.113
Heteroskedasticity	White	The probability of observed R-squared	0.391	0.914

Table 3. The result of the normality, heteroskedasticity, autocorrelation, and multicollinearity examination

Examination Required	The Technique	Measurement	The results	
			Model 1: IS = f(SBN, SBI)	Model 2: FV = f (IS)
Multicollinierity	Variance Inflation Factor (VIF)	The related value for SBN and SBI	VIF for SBN and SBI is 1.009	N.A.

N.A.= Not available

Table 4 presents the estimation results of the path analysis model, including the p-values for SBN and SBI of 0.0358 and 0.0510, respectively (see Model 1). These values are lower than the 10% relaxed significance level. Therefore, the size of the supervisory board positively affects income smoothing. Conversely, the supervisory board's independence has an inverse influence on income smoothing. Besides, the p-value for IS in Model 2 is 0.7114, higher than 10%; therefore, income smoothing does not affect firm value.

Table 4. The estimation result of the path analysis model

Model 1: IS = f(SBN, SBI)				Model 2: FS = f(IS)			
Determinant	Coefficient	t-statistic	Probability	Determinant	Coefficient	t-statistic	Probability
C	1.100944	0.964064	0.3389	C	8.251702	51.94707	0.0000
SBN	0.224188	2.147467	0.0358	IS	-0.033744	-0.371643	0.7114
SBI	-4.150279	-1.991105	0.0510				

V. DISCUSSION

This study finds a positive association between supervisory board size and income smoothing. Therefore, it confirms agency theory, suggesting a small board size. Given its small size, the supervisory board can recognize each other appropriately, discuss issues effectively, and reach a correct consensus (Lipton & Lorsch, 1992). Furthermore, Lipton and Lorsch (1992) suggest that the preferred small size is below 8 or 9 people. Regarding the income-smoothing reduction, this small size is efficacious, as confirmed by Ratnaningsih and Mashelia (2020).

This study finds a negative association between supervisory board independence and income smoothing. According to agency theory, independent supervisors represent the interests of public shareholders. They must detect and prevent opportunistic behavior by top managers (Fathelbab & Abu Quba, 2025). Regarding the income-smoothing reduction, this greater portion is effective, as confirmed by Ekadjaja et al. (2020), Dickson (2021), and Maryanti et al. (2023).

This study locates a meaningless relationship between income smoothing and firm value, similar to Kirana (2020) and Ozundu et al. (2025). In our research context, using a path analysis model, this situation occurs because the effectiveness of the supervisory board, as reflected in its size and independence, can mitigate managerial tendencies to smooth income; hence, the adverse effect of income smoothing disappears in the market.

VI. CONCLUSION

Income smoothing (IS) should be reduced; therefore, this investigation aims to explore the influence of the supervisory board's effectiveness, as mirrored by size and independence, on IS, as well as the impact of IS on firm value. After examining non-financial enterprises in LQ45 between 2017 and 2023, this investigation finds that a small supervisory board and a large proportion of independent directors are essential to curtail managerial action to smooth earnings. Additionally, this tendency can counteract the adverse effect of IS on the market, as evidenced by the weak association between IS and stock prices used to measure company value. This investigation uses only a few determinants of income smoothing and examines the relationship between IS and company value for non-financial companies in the LQ45 index. Therefore, subsequent scholars are advised to inspect the gender diversity of the supervisory board and the number of meetings as additional determinants of IS. Furthermore, to make a broader generalization, this investigation recommends that they use non-financial enterprises listed on the Indonesian Stock Exchange as the objects. If possible, the use of related companies across Southeast Asian capital markets can be implemented.

ACKNOWLEDGMENT

The authors appreciate Maranatha Christian University for funding this research process and covering the article processing charge for this publication.

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